

FUZZY FRONT END AND DESIGNING TOWARDS A RAISON D'ÊTRE

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Keywords: design education, Design Vision, VIP

ABSTRACT

Presenting a newly developed design course, reflecting on it, and extracting important learning towards understanding differences between Novice and Master designers. New methods and techniques are being introduced, among others, the VIP approach, or Vision in Product Design, the Saturday Special Edition as an alternative format to collect and present results from design analysis, and a comprehensive process to move from a company's Fuzzy Front End of Innovation to a concrete product concept for that company.

A word of appreciation and gratitude to the colleagues of PO3, in particular to Matthijs van Dijk for co-designing this course, and Pieter Desmet, Evelinde van Dorp, Mariska Rooth and Myrthe Yeh, for their great energy and inspiration while implementing this new course.

INTRODUCTION

PO3, or 'The Fuzzy Front End', is the third design course in a series of five in the Bachelor program for Industrial Design Engineering at the TU Delft. PO1, Introduction to Design, and PO2, Conceptualization, focus on general design competencies and on creating a product concept for some given design problem. Some of the elements explored in these courses are the basic design cycle, a design brief, user observation and interviews, idea generation, idea selection, sketching, conceptualizing, presenting and reflecting on one's process and learning. In PO3, the design process is extended in a number of ways:

1. A CLIENT COMPANY AND THE FUZZY FRONT END OF INNOVATION

What might happen before the actual conceptualization phase, dealing with strategic aspects of product design as seen from the viewpoint

Table 1: Overview Design Courses in the IDE Bachelor

of a client company: which products could this company plan to design to secure a successful future. This ought to result in a strategic opportunity field for which the student team and the client decide to proceed with in developing new product concepts (Buijs, 1992 & 2000).

In PO3 both invented and real company cases may be used, the company being represented by an IDE staff member playing that role.

2. USER-PRODUCT INTERACTION IN A FUTURE CONTEXT

A second learning objective is that we develop a Design Vision on what the Interaction between User and Product in a particular Context could or ought to be. This is done using a process called VIP or Vision in Product design (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011). This phase results in a Design Vision and a Product Development Brief that we use as the starting point for the third phase, that of Product Conceptualization.

3. PRODUCT CONCEPTUALISATION

This 3rd and last phase is not really a new competence as students have already experienced this in earlier exercises (PO1 and PO2). However the complexity of elements to be taken into account is increasing, having to design in the context of a client company and working with a clear design vision on interaction as formulated earlier on. Also, as the project takes place in a relationship with a client company, a business plan and a market introduction plan have to be formulated.

Next to the earlier three levels and phases with their respective learning objectives, extra competencies have been defined as learning objectives for this design project.

4. SUSTAINABILITY

Based on McDonough & Braungart’s Cradle to Cradle approach (McDonough & Braungart, 2002) and Ehrenfeld’s ideas on Sustainable Well-Being (Ehrenfeld, 2008), a fourth learning objective in this design project is Sustainability. In our present

Three Systems or 3 levels of abstraction

Figure 1. Three phases of Design - moving three abstraction levels

society, it is becoming unacceptable to put products in the world without paying special attention to sustainability: social, economic and environmental. As such students are asked to develop all their deliverables (e.g. company strategy, design vision, product concepts, and a market introduction plan) taking into account sustainability as an explicit consideration, demonstrating sustainability effects of their proposals at each stage of the process.

5. RAISON D'ÊTRE

And finally, having produced a design for this specific client based on a projected interaction vision, one should be able to articulate and present what one may call the 'Raison d'être' of the final product concept. In other words a legitimization for why the design has resulted in what it is. It is about being able to make meaningful connections in terms of a fit with (1) society, (2) the client company and (3) the user. One might say that when all the earlier competencies (1 till 4) are covered, this Raison d'être is like the icing on the cake. Being able to articulate and present such a 'Raison d'être' can now be seen as the main objective of this design course.

In Figure 1, the three main stages of the whole PO3 process are presented. Describing the Process through its main mile stones and deliverables:

MEETING 1: PITCH & PROJECT INTAKE (WEEK 1 OR 2)

1. Identity and approach (values, ambitions and priorities) of the design team;
2. Problem statement as observed - to be checked with the client;
3. Initial ideas about possible strategic directions (including sustainability considerations);
4. A project proposal for the first part of the project: defining a business strategy for product development.

MEETING 2: NEW BUSINESS STRATEGY (WEEK 3)

1. An understanding of the present and future position of the company in its markets and in society;
2. Objectives for the innovation project;

3. Specific opportunities, coupled to (unique) strengths or core competencies of the company;
4. A domain, described in terms of a human activity or need in some societal context or location.

MEETING 3: VISION ON INTERACTION, CARTOON AND FUTURE PRODUCT 2020 (WEEK 6)

The Saturday Special Edition - containing

1. A study of the present and a new context for the chosen domain (2020);
2. A vision on user interaction for the human activity or need defined in the first phase;
3. A cartoon, illustrating this vision on interaction.
4. A 2020 product idea (in the form of a simple sketch, like one might draw on a napkin).

Figure 2: One page from an 8 page Saturday Special

MEETING 4: PRODUCT DESIGN BRIEF, DESIGN CRITERIA AND 2014 CONCEPT (WEEK 7)

1. The Product Development Brief
2. The main criteria to assess the quality of the concepts (including sustainability and well-being considerations)
3. The first ideas for a 2014 concept(s) and how it is developing.

MEETING 5: DESIGN, MARKETING PLAN & RAISON D'ÊTRE (WEEK 9)

1. 3D Model and Poster describing product and interaction in context;
2. Detailed design (a.o. main components, materials, aesthetics and main usage ideas).
3. Business Plan and Market introduction;
4. Effect of new product on Sustainability, Interaction and Business Strategy;
5. Evaluation of the outcome in relation to earlier formulated goals for this project.

At the end of the exercise (week 10 of the project), there is an open conversation between the student team, the coach and the client, now talking openly about each other's roles, the process, project planning and organization, surprising events, the presentations, probably also addressing some frustrating or tensed moments during the project, but hopefully also including many good experiences.

EXPLORING LEARNING OBJECTIVES

We make a distinction between Generic competencies and Specific competencies. Generic Competencies are competencies that will come back in most design tasks, things like Imagining, Sketching, Presenting and Reflecting. This is basic to a designer, like reading and writing for the common man, and it is through repeated exercise combined with reflective moments that these competencies develop over time.

Next to these generic competencies, there are course specific competencies, competencies that may become relevant in specific design tasks. One might see these like tools in a toolkit that are selected depending on particular design activities.

With the new bachelor program (Roozenburg et al, 2006) a competence monitor system was introduced, which encompasses all the courses in the curriculum. For PO3, the following list of competencies was defined (ref. Zijlstra & vd Zwet, 2010):

1. The student is familiar with different approaches for new-product strategy development and is capable of developing and selecting a proper approach or method to that end.

2. The student can formulate research questions in the context of new-product development planning and execute some of these research tasks within a product development process.
3. The student is capable of evaluating new product strategy proposals and product concepts on sustainability aspects, in other words on social, economic and environmental aspects.
4. The student can develop a vision as to the development of a product portfolio for the client organization.
5. The student is capable of analyzing the User-Product interaction in a particular context and developing new product concepts from this perspective.
6. The student can develop a vision on User - Product interaction using a VIP (Vision in Product development) approach.
7. The student can set up a business plan for the implementation of a new product design, including a market introduction plan.
8. The student is able to communicate and present strategic ideas and product proposals in a convincing and inspiring manner.
9. The student is capable of applying creative techniques to develop new product concepts.
10. The student learns to work in teams and acquires basic skills in project management.

With four editions of PO3 behind us, we can say that most of these objectives are reasonably well covered, and with each new event, the course is being further developed and improved in accordance with these learning objectives.

While designing this course there was a need to be more specific in determining competencies and main themes for PO3. An inspiration for this approach was found in the VIP approach itself (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011). In the VIP process one clearly distinguishes three elements: (1) context, (2) user - product interaction and (3) a resulting product design. Using this as an inspiration for a better understanding of competencies, similarly three focus points were identified: (see Table 2)

1. The student him/herself (left column in Table 2): attitude, values and aspirations.
2. Theoretical concepts (right column in Table 2) like design methodology, design tools and techniques, and knowledge of materials, strength, ergonomics, etc. things that generally speaking, may be looked up in books and applied when needed.
3. Interacting ‘in the world’ (middle column in Table 2): making things happen: design, creating, selecting, reflecting, communicating, etc., all verbs (activities) and what one may see as the original designation of the term competence education: to learn (how) to make things happen in the world.

Having such a principle to distinguish competencies helps to elaborate certain ideas on coaching and assessing student’s work. Each column may require a different approach. So, for example, attributing a formal score to a student’s attitude may be questionable, as the incidental interaction and dynamics between a coach and a student may be determining for such a score and as such not be very

objective. But that doesn’t mean these would be irrelevant, quite the contrary. Such items have to be addressed and reflected upon. Also, assuming a systemic principle of a ‘self-same’ mechanism (principles being replicated at different points in a system), the attitude and values of individual coaches become relevant in the sense that they can be role models to the students. A useful term in this context is ‘enculturing’, that is to cherish and propagate certain values and qualities in an organization (here, in a design studio) and as such develop what one may call a designerly attitude among students.

In the following paragraphs, some of the specific PO3 competencies are being further developed and described.

The starting point for a competence learning situation is that it is based on experience and reflection. In combination with promoting intrinsic motivation with the students, we want to focus on the actual design task, including the option that process steps can go wrong without immediately implying an insufficient grade. On the basis of the individual reflections afterwards, coaches can look at individual learning, and look at the kind of

Competencies:

values / criteria /attitude	domain / application / skills	techniques / procedures / knowledge
taking initiative	conceptualising	morphological analysis
intrinsic motivation	presenting convincingly	techniques for idea generation
a belief in free will	negotiating	reflection techniques
daring to make a statement	managing oneself	Lid’s wheel
creating meaning	managing one’s team	Kolb experiential learning
fantasy and inspiration	doing research	VIP approach
scope in time, space & complexity	setting up a design process	Basic Design Cycle
to know oneself in creative processes	decision making	Criteria and concept evaluation
reflective practice	managing contacts with client	Scenario’s / Roadmapping
ethics, sustainable well-being	finding inspirations	SWOT analysis
design is a wonderful profession	etc.	Business Plan
etc.		etc

Table 2. Three categories of Competencies

elements brought into this reflective discussion, e.g. connections with methodology, project management, involvement of the client, etc.

So, for PO3, next to a formal list of learning objectives, and inspired by a ‘Raison d’être’ idea of the project, the PO3 design team formulated some more qualitative objectives.

REFINING LEARNING OBJECTIVES

RAISON D’ÊTRE

At first sight, one might not think of this as a Competence in terms of being able to achieve something or apply some method. But it does fit the left column in Table 2, in the sense that it may be seen as part of a design attitude; to be conscious of ‘Why and how something (a product) is relevant to the world and to the people who will interact with it’. As designers, we are not just developing inanimate objects. One might even argue that the object itself is only a material expression of something more essential, describing why it is what it is, and how it relates to people and/or how it influences people and their interactions with their surroundings.

Getting used to think in terms of ‘Raison d’être’ is an important capacity of designers. When observing or designing an object, a designer should almost automatically switch to questions like: what kind of behavior does this object invite to, what is its significance, what metaphors could ‘sit’ at the core of its design, and which associations does it evoke in terms of meaning. As such, objects should always be looked at in relation to some interaction and in a context of time, location and a cultural surrounding. This idea of a ‘Raison d’être’ can easily be connected with the ideas coming forth from sustainability and Sustainable Well-Being (e.g. Ehrenfeld, 2008). In today’s world, it is hard to imagine developing products without taking into account this ethical aspect of survival, whether it be social, economic or environmental. As such, the ‘Raison d’être’ is a justification for the existence of that particular object in an evolving context. The object is not some singular isolated object anymore, it now has meaning and should be seen and presented in connection to human needs, values and customs.

- Proper information gathering
- Idea generation: creative – surprising – challenging
- Synthesis: coherence, integration and common sense
- Time Scope: next product generations in Future Context
- A Good story: reliable, innovative, interesting and clear
- Demonstrating sustainability: social, environmental and economical
- Good fit product concept and corporate identity / market situation
- Clear and convincing presentations
- Reflections: sharp and constructive, connecting experience and theory

Table 3. Qualitative learning Objectives

QUALITIES AND CRITERIA

“Everything of Value is Vulnerable” (Original citation in Dutch: “Alles van Waarde is Weerloos”, Lucebert, 1974). ‘Real’ value, or the essence of something may be hard to express, let alone measure and as such vulnerable in selection processes, negotiation and decision-making. When developing a vision for what a product should mean to future users, chances are that the first expressions of such visions will demand rather a lot of “suspension of disbelief” from a client and students will have to think about how to present and decide upon such interim results.

As an example, Clarck & Fujimoto in their HBR paper “The Power of Product Integrity” (1991), state:

“Product integrity is much broader than basic functionality or technical performance. Customers who have accumulated experience with a product expect new models to balance basic functions and economy with more subtle characteristics. Consumers expect new products to harmonize with their values and lifestyles.” Such a fit is something that needs to be looked at with great care, especially in the earlier stages of a product development process. Clients may have difficulties in judging the consequences of certain choices at these early stages. While applying the VIP process (Hekkert and van Dijk, 2011), it becomes even more ‘subtle’ or intangible, now addressing an interaction, without yet having any notion of a product.

Back to Clarck and Fujimoto. At some point they describe how a team of Honda designers ‘pinpoint’ their new concept as a “Pocket Rocket”. This now was the symbolic/metaphoric term with which the new concept was to be designed and judged by. How does one judge concepts on their fit with such a metaphor? Whereas Roozenburg en Eekels (1991) mention two kinds of Criteria (Demands and Wishes) and shortly mention Specifications, four ‘grades’ of criteria are proposed: (1) Specifications, (2) Demands, (3) Wishes and finally (4) Qualities. To expand on Qualities - In the example of the “Pocket Rocket”, one might interpret this as compact, spicy, fast, powerful and friendly (as examples) but it is the designer’s task to elaborate such abstract qualities into more tangible forms, e.g. in the form of adjectives or collages. Using

adjectives is one way to articulate such intangible qualities (ref. Muller 2001). Other techniques are cartoons depicting an interaction and collages. In PO3, we have introduced another format for a design analysis report, namely a “Saturday Special Edition” newspaper format (see above for example). This format permits one to preserve some of the richness of the context study (colors, anecdotes, interviews, cartoons, etc.).

In this course, operating at “The Fuzzy Front End”, we need tools to evaluate ideas and concepts not yet articulated into measurable designs and prototypes. And similarly, these concepts are to embody emergent qualities as described in a vision on interaction. Some kind of “Suspension of Disbelief” may be demanded here, both from the designer’s and from the client’s point of view, as some interaction qualities have to be extrapolated from yet limited information. It is the ability to visualize or ‘pre-sense’ the consequences of such early design considerations that forms an extremely valuable learning objective on a path from novice designer to master designer. Lawson & Dorst (2009) address this issue in the sense that master designers have grown a much stronger capacity to oversee such consequences compared to novice designers. Here in this PO3 project, we address these capacities explicitly, in different forms (future context, defining interaction qualities and first creating a 2020 concept and using this as an inspiration for a more realistic and feasible 2014 concept.

THE VIP PROCESS

A large part of the PO3 design exercise is taken up by parts of the VIP process as developed in recent years by Paul Hekkert and Matthijs van Dijk (2011). The VIP process consists of 2 main activities, one, a deconstructive analysis around an existing product in a given domain followed by a creative process generating a new product for a future context. Given the limited amount of time and the integration of this part of the process with other design procedures only the 2nd half of this process is used. (fig. 3).

Figure 3. VIP Process (source Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011)

Having generated and defined a business opportunity in the 1st part of the project, students now do an extensive study of the domain for which they plan to design a new product. All kinds of aspects for the future that is designed for, around users and society, are being collected and in the end presented in the form of a Saturday Special Edition Newspaper. One can think of state-of-the-art developments, developing-world customs, interviews with famous people about what this domain may be developing into, anecdotes, historical developments, new technologies, problems with present functions, etc. etc. In the VIP approach itself, one looks for four kinds of information: (1) trends, (2) developments, (3) states and (4) principles.

The idea for the Newspaper format, and a more journalistic stance (as opposed to a more formal textual report with illustrations) is that more 'experiential' richness can be collected and presented. The goal is to grow an appreciation for a wide array of information and possible complexity of the domain in the future, appreciating what is really of importance, later on providing leads for idea generation. The following steps consist of deciding

what the most important (future) elements or dynamics users in the given context will have to deal with. We ask the students to understand such driving forces and their interrelations, as one whole. Without this notion of coherence it is impossible to take a position as a designer defining what is going on in this future world, in how people live their lives or if you want to create a different human behavior and interaction in the light of this future context. This statement is a crucial step in VIP. It allows the student to take a stance as to how future users will behave. Because of this we say that in taking such a stance (for him and herself and or the company he or she works for) lies the responsibility of the designer. The statement can be defined as follows:

1. We (the designer together with the people he or she is working for) want people to . . . (experience, appreciate, be able to . . .) followed by definitions on a future interaction that accomplishes this goal set in the statement. This is followed by a description of a set of product qualities that causes or evokes this interaction:
2. 'Therefore a Product-User interaction should . . .'

and

3. 'Thus the product should . . .'.

This part of the process results in a product development brief and a list of criteria with which to proceed to the 3rd and last phase of PO3, that of product conceptualization.

REFLECTIONS AND DISCUSSION

Having experienced four editions of this design course, each time adapting and further developing the course, while reacting on comments from students and coaches, a number of 'sensitive' issues can be identified.

First of all, the aspirations might be ambitious. Pushing students to deliver designs with an explicitly created and articulated 'Raison d'être' is not an easy task for young 2nd year students. And as a matter of fact, not even to all the coaches who have to 'sell' such a perspective to their students. So, maybe we are kind of 'pushing against a rope'.

Extending a capacity to view things from different (interrelated) frames of reference can also be found in the structure of the course as it moves through three abstraction levels: (1) business strategy, (2) user interaction in context and finally (3) the design of some object (also see Fig. 1).

Comments from students were collected from the Competence Monitoring system recently implemented in the new IDE Delft Bachelor Design program (Zijlstra & van der Zwet, 2010). It consists of relatively open questions giving some lead as to guide the student's reflections, but not so far as specifying any concrete techniques or qualities as addressed in this course. By looking at this input from the students one can judge in how far specific comments are made addressing competencies and qualities as targeted in this exercise.

The students coached by the author seem to appreciate many of the aspects described above, mentioning most of these. As such one might conclude that the Raison d'être of PO3 is in itself achievable. But looking at other students, one sees differences and while reading these, one might come to different conclusions. Some of these reflections are similar to the ones from students coached by the author; others are rather abstract and/or superficial. More study will be needed to grasp the exact reasons for such observations. Hypothesizing, the role of the

coach seems important (is he or she challenging the students sufficiently?), or does this new Competence Monitoring system have a demotivating effect on certain students, the system being automated and not visibly interactive. And of course, students are different, thinking in terms of Kolb Learning Styles or MBTI types, e.g. leading to differences of concreteness in their descriptions.

Next to studying a number of student's reflections, a focus group meeting with staff was held. From this a number of remarks were collected:

- Some students (teams) have problems with the 'fuzziness' of the exercise, others feel very happy to have the freedom to develop ideas at will; comment from the author: exactly one of the challenges for PO3 - to experience oneself in creative processes and develop something Rollo May called 'The Courage to Create' (May, 1975).
- An interesting comment: "If you want to be more than a 'shape giver', you need to look behind the curtain" - nice metaphor to describe one of the objectives of PO3: thinking in terms of "Raison d'être".
- Little emphasis on sustainability, less than one would like to see.
- "With hindsight, would like to do the whole process again" - comment: this is the first time students go through such a process and it is difficult if not impossible to oversee the consequences of certain design moves without prior experience of the whole process.
- "The whole process is rather complex and actually too complex for these students and the exercise should be simplified" - comment: not sure about this and important question to envisage for the future.
- Collaborating with real companies (as opposed to simulated cases) very motivating to students - comment: yes, but complexity and fuzziness is increased and demands more from students; not sure whether this is a learning objective by itself. It may take away precious time from experiencing some of the primary objectives of the course.

To come back to competencies as addressed in PO3, students are to look further than just the immediate present. To design for today's context is irrelevant,

today is history. Students have to (try to) collect an image of a future context including developments and trends in society, technological developments, etc. To this end students have to create two concepts, one for a far away future (some two product generations into the future, e.g. for 2020) and then with this as an inspiration, develop some concept that may be feasible as the next product generation (e.g. 2014). This 'stretch' helps in two ways, first the already mentioned idea that one does not design for today, but also in terms of facilitating a creative process. The 2020 concept doesn't have to be feasible (in a business or technical sense), it can be seen as a first expression or articulation of the envisioned interaction as defined in the previous stage of defining a Design Vision. As such it helps to prevent that wonderful ideas are 'pushed off the stage' only because they were not made explicit enough or tangible enough (in terms of communicating and sharing with other stakeholders) at the time of translating such qualities into a tangible product. Introducing such a 'transitional' step may be an important element in both the creative process itself and in maintaining a shared understanding with all the parties involved in the process. Of course, this demands that one creates an attitude of 'suspension of disbelief'. The ideas presented may at first look rather futuristic and unrealistic to an uninformed audience. This (what one might call a) bottleneck is something that students bump into when having to present to a (simulated) client at that stage of the process. The suspension of disbelief has to do with properly considering some hypothetical situation and think through its consequences, much like in a chess game - 'if I were to move that piece in such and such a way, what would happen on the board?' Another issue that might be further investigated is the idea from Karl Weick (Weick, 1995) that during an analysis, we (human beings) tend to have a concept in mind while analyzing a system (e.g. the context of the user-product interaction). So,

although in the prescribed process we pretend to concentrate on the analysis of the system itself or on describing some interaction, we base our viewpoint on more or less conscious pre-images or prototypes of outcomes. According to Weick, this image of an outcome (a future design) might be a leading principle for our analysis; in other words, a potential outcome is used as an hypothesis to guide our information gathering. We are not just collecting information; we are implicitly testing an hypothesis. And when we come against contradicting information, we might not notice it, or, if consciously noticing such contradiction, generate a new hypothetical concept to guide us further. No conclusion is formulated here, except that this may be a starting point for some interesting research in the application of the VIP process.

Summarizing some of the questions for further reflection and development of PO3:

1. to what extend do the qualitative learning objectives 'land' with our students, in how far are they now integrated and e.g. seen back in later design projects?
2. How hard is it for students to think in terms of a 2020 context and a 2020 concept - maybe in relation to particular techniques like Back-casting and the Future Perfect?
3. In how far is "Suspension of Disbelief" important in the context of student presentations to clients?
4. Should one reduce the set of learning objectives for PO3 or leave it as it is?
5. What is the effectiveness of the coaches and clients in terms of realizing PO3 objectives, and what might be necessary to improve this, e.g. by explicitly addressing competencies of design staff.

Figure 4. Self supporting foldable tent, and afterwards simply stuff it in your bag.

Figure 5. Redefining the tent - both individual and shared space - a whole 'village' under one cover.

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